

**PROCEEDINGS OF THE 67TH
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SOCIETY OF
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TECHNOLOGY

**SWST 67th
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Advancing Regenerative Sustainability with Wood Science

**JUNE 30 – JULY 5, 2024
GRAND HOTEL BERNARDIN
PORTOROŽ, SLOVENIA**

**Ilona Peszlen, President-Elect
Angela Haney, Executive Director**

Edited by Jeffrey Morrell

On behalf of the Society, I would like to thank all of those who attended the meeting and presented their research. I'd especially like to thank all of the students who attended and hope that they join us at future meetings.

Finally, I'd like to thank our Executive Director, Angela Haney, for organizing an excellent meeting and Jeff Morrell for assembling these proceedings. We hope you find them useful and look forward to seeing you all June 15-20, 2025, in Fort Collins, Colorado for our 68th Annual meeting.

Ilona Peszlen, SWST President

In-service performance of untreated and Biofinish coated Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.)

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ABSTRACT

The service life of timber products exposed to natural weathering is a critical concern for their use in external building elements. Coatings have traditionally served as a protective measure, yet their degradation over time necessitates frequent maintenance or replacement, incurring costs and environmental concerns. Biofinish, an innovative *Aureobasidium pullulans*-based coating, offers protective and self-healing properties inspired by biological processes. By reducing maintenance needs, Biofinish enhances wood's durability and environmental friendliness, unlocking its full potential in construction. This advancement is essential for improving the sustainability and longevity of timber products.

The goal of this study was to investigate the in-service performance of an innovative bioinspired living coating system. The performance of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) wood coated with Biofinish was compared with uncoated references. Samples were exposed to natural weathering for 12 months under the climatic conditions of Izola, Slovenia representing warm temperate climates (Cfa). The colour changes, wettability, glossiness, and surface roughness were measured as indicators of weathering progress. Assessment of fungal diversity on wood surfaces before weathering, after 3, 6, and 12 months of exposure was performed to evaluate the protective properties against wood-infesting fungi and assess the survival of *A. pullulans* within the coating. Results revealed that the total colour changes (ΔE) of Biofinish-coated wood were negligible. However, untreated Scots pine wood revealed colour changes already after one month of exposure. The gloss changes for both types of samples were small. The contact angle measured on Biofinish-coated wood was higher compared to that of uncoated Scots pine. Surface roughness of uncoated wood increased due to the erosion effect caused by the weathering progress. Fungus *A. pullulans* was the dominant species found on both uncoated and Biofinish-coated wood, suggesting its survival and effective antagonistic action against other wood-decaying fungi. These findings highlight the Biofinish coating's superior aesthetic performance against natural weathering and its potential for self-healing properties due to the survival of *A. pullulans*.